

PRODUCTION OF BULK COST-EFFECTIVE MAGNESIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Magnesium matrix composites overcome many demerits of Mg alloys, such as low stiffness and low strengths, so they promise wide application in lightweight fields. However, magnesium matrix composites are limitedly used because of high cost. Their high cost usually comes from three aspects: reinforcements, fabrication and secondary deformation. Thus, economical particles and high efficient production should be employed.

Micron-SiC particles (SiCp) are cheap besides their high mechanical properties. SiC Among all of these methods, stirring casting is regarded as the most productive and economical one and semi-solid stirring could disperse the particles cluster,, but long stir time is needed to obtain good particle distribution, which often brings too much gas and oxidation to Mg matrix. Thus, it is necessary to reduce the stir time. Fortunately, ultrasonic vibration presents a good route to solve the particle distribution. It was reported that the acoustic cavitation effect would produce a lot of ultrasonic cavitation in the melting metal, which would collapse with high pressure(above1000atm), temperature(~5000°C) and heating and cooling rates(above 1010 K/s). This would disperse the existed agglomeration consisted of micro-SiC and clean the surface of SiC particles. In addition, ultrasonic vibration can effectively outgas Mg melting. Therefore, ultrasonic vibration is very effective to disperse particles without gas and oxidation. However, it is very difficult or time-consuming to add particles to melting using single ultrasonic vibration. What's more, the effect of ultrasonic vibration is very micro-localized. Thus, single ultrasonic vibration may be not a good method to fabricate micron-particle reinforced Mg matrix composites. If mechanical stir is combined assisted by ultrasonic vibration, the above disadvantages of mechanical stir and ultrasonic vibration can be well overcome. Thus, in this work, we combine stirring casting with ultrasonic vibration and try to explore the proper method to fabricate the bulk SiCp

reinforced magnesium composite with good mechanical performance and particle distribution.

SiCp Addition significantly reduces the plasticity of Mg matrix, so it is necessary to develop the secondary processing for magnesium matrix composites to exploit their benefits (application). Extrusion is the best route for achieving a combination of the hot compaction and mechanical working, which yields a full integrity wrought material. So extrusion is an increasingly attractive processing route for a class of materials which has typically been amongst the most difficult to work successfully. Thus, hot extrusion of Mg matrix composites is also investigated.

2 Experiments

2.1 Fabrication of the composites

10 μ m20vol.% SiCp/AZ91D Mg matrix composites were fabricated. AZ91D alloy was selected as the matrix. SiCp in the average diameter of 10 μ m were selected as the reinforcement. The illustration of the fabrication device is show in Fig.1.The ultrasonic device consists of a transducer coupled with a maximum power of 2 KW and frequency of 20 KHz. In the beginning, AZ91 alloy was placed into the mild steel crucible, and then it was melt under the protection atmosphere of mixed CO₂/SF₆. Then, after the temperature of melt reached 720°C, it was cooling down to the semi-solid temperature and then the preheated micron-SiC particles were added into the melt with stirring. After semi-solid stir, the melt were heated until it turned out to be liquid and ultrasonic probe was dipped into the melt. At the same time, the melt is stirred without vortexin hand with ultrasonic treatment. Finally, the melt was cast into a preheated mould and solidified under about 100MPa. The temperature-time sequence for the stir casting assisted by ultrasonic processing is shown in Fig.2. Fig. 3 is the picture of SiCp/AZ91 composites

fabricated by mechanical stir assisted by ultrasonic. The bulk ingot was more than 20kg.

Fig.1 Illustration of the fabrication device

Fig.2 The temperature-time sequence for the stir casting assisted by ultrasonic.

Fig.3 The image of the bulk composite

2.2 Extrusion of the composites

The extrusion billets of the composite were cut from the large sizes. The billets were solutionized at 415°C for 24 hours (T4 treatment). The extrusions were conducted using a press with a 2000 KN load limit. The billets, pressure pad and dish-shaped die were put into the extrusion container. The extrusion container was heated to the given temperatures in a muffle furnace. The temperatures of the container were monitored using a K-type thermocouple inserted into the hole drilled in the container. Once the container attained the desired temperatures, a period of 1 hour was allowed to elapse before the extrusion was carried out. This time is long enough to allow the billet to reach a steady-state temperature, as determined from previous tests. The billets were extruded using extrusion ratios 12:1 and extrusion temperatures 350°C. Extrudates were immediately cooled in water in order to obtain real-time microstructures while extrusions are accomplished. In order to compare with the composite, AZ91 alloy was also extruded in the same conditions as the composite.

2.3 Aging of the composites

As-cast and as-extruded composites after T4 treatment was aged at 165 °C with different temperatures. The tensile mechanical properties of the aged composites were tested in order to obtain the peaked aging processing.

2.4 Material characterization

Microstructural examination was carried out by optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscope (SEM) and transmission electron microscope (TEM). For OM, SEM and TEM, specimens were cut parallel to extrusion direction by electrodischarge. The specimens for OM were ground, polished and etched in acetic picral [5 ml acetic acid + 6g picric acid + 10ml H₂O + 100 ml ethanol (95%)]. Specimens for TEM were prepared by grinding-polishing the sample to produce a foil of 50µm thickness followed by punching 3mm diameter disks. The disks were ion beam thinned. Specimens for SEM were ground and polished with great care in order to avoid causing particle damage in this stage.

2.5 Mechanical testing

The tensile mechanical properties of SiCp/AZ91 composites and alloys before and after extrusion were

measured by using an Instron1186 universal testing machine at a constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. The size and shape of the tensile test samples is shown in Fig.4. The tensile property data (yield strength/YS, ultimate tensile strength/UTS, elastic modulus/E and elongation/ δ) were based on the average of 3-5 tests.

Fig.4 The size and shape of the tensile test samples.

3 Results

3.1 Microstructure of as-cast composite ingot

It is very necessary for bulk metal matrix composites to investigate the particle content and distribution because of its large size. The particle distribution of the bulk composite ingot is shown in Fig.5. The particle distribution was similar in different positions. The particle distribution was uniform in general. In addition From Fig.5, the particle contents were almost same in those positions. Table.1 shows the density of samples in the different positions corresponding to the Fig.5. It can be found that density slightly varied, which further proved that particle contents were uniform in the bulk ingots. This also indicated that the settlement of SiCp was not evident during the solidification course of the composites.

Although particle macro-clusters were not observed, and particle distributions were fairly uniform, as shown in Fig.5. However, most particles were segregated along grain boundaries in the micro-scale level, as shown in Fig.6. Many particles distributed along grain boundaries, like necklaces. This is very normal for metal matrix composites fabricated by stir casting. This kind particle distribution is called “necklace-type”, which is caused by the “push” effect of solidification front. During the solidification of the composites produced by stir casting, most particles were pushed to the solidification front while primary magnesium grains grew, so these particles were segregated in the intergranular regions during the impingement with other growing grains. For the large ingots, the solidification speed is much slower than

that in the small ingots. Thus, the “necklace-type” particle distribution is more popular in the larger ingots.

Table.1 The density (g/cm³) of samples in the different positions corresponding to the Fig.5

Position	A0	A1	A2	B
Density	2.083	2.087	2.079	2.103
Average	2.088±0.015			

3.2 Microstructure of as-extruded composite

Fig.7 shows the longitudinal particle distributions of the as-extruded composites. It is found by comparing Figs.5-7 that the particle distribution was significantly improved by extrusion. The “necklace-type” particle distribution was almost eliminated by extrusion in the longitudinal direction So the particle distribution was much more uniform in as-extruded composite. This can evidently improve the mechanical properties of the composite.

However, some particles were fractured along the direction perpendicular to the extrusion direction, as shown in Fig. 8. Our previous study indicates that the damage induced by extrusion is sensitive to the particle content on a local scale. The extrusion-induced damage to the reinforcement has been observed in aluminum matrix composites, and the damage was found to increase with particle size, volume fraction and aspect ratio. And it is reported that particle size is refined by particle fracture during extrusion in aluminum matrix composite. This refinement was also observed in this study, as shown in Figs.5-7. During the reduction of the cross-section of the composite billet in the extrusion die, the matrix alloy is deformed in a plastic manner while the ceramic particles tend to fragment because they are rigid and non-deformable. Finite element simulations by Christamn have shown significant triaxial stresses were developed within the composite matrix during plastic deformation, due to the constraint imposed by the reinforcement. A particle is cracked when the local stress acting on the particle exceeds its fracture strength. And there are the pre-existing flaws in the particles. So there are particle cracked in the SiCp/AZ91 composite during extrusion. In addition, the particle content of the bulk composite is 20%, so the particle space is very close. Assuming element of

Fig.5. The particle distribution in different positions of the bulk composite ingot

Fig. 6 The typical “necklace-type” particle distribution in large composite ingot. (a) $\times 1000$, (b) $\times 2000$

closely spaced particles in the composites with high SiCp contents as two SiC particles separated by a matrix layer of thickness h and length b , some estimates of the stress level generated in the matrix can be obtained. Using the analogy of the plane strain compression of a block between two elastic platens, and applying the standard force with sticking friction at the interface, the maximum stress developed in the matrix can be calculated by the following equation:

$$\sigma_{\max} = \sigma_F \left(1 + \frac{b}{2h} \right) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 7 The longitudinal particle distributions of the as-extruded composites (a) $\times 500$, (b) $\times 1000$

And the more closely spaced particles imposed greater constraint on the plastic flow in the ductile matrix thereby generating higher triaxial stresses, when the reinforcement volume fraction was increased. So there are many particles fractured in the present composite, due to the higher stress produced during extrusion.

3.3 Ageing behaviors of the composites

The ageing behaviors of as-cast and as-extruded composites are shown in Figs.9 and 10. For as-cast composite, UTS and elastic modulus generally increased with the increase of ageing time until peak

Fig.8 Particle cracking in as-extruded composite.
(a) $\times 8000$, (b) $\times 16000$

ageing took place at 24 hours, as shown in Fig.9. After peak ageing, UTS and elastic modulus decreased as ageing time increased. For as-extruded composite, peak-ageing occurred at 22 hours. Extrusion did not significantly affect the ageing behavior. Thus, T6 treatments of as-cast composite and as-extruded composite are ageing 24 hours after T4 treatment and 22 hours after T4 treatment, respectively.

The microstructure of peak-aged as-extruded composite was shown in Fig.11. There were a great number of lamellate precipitations. The precipitations

Fig. 9 Ageing behavior of as-cast composite
(a) UTS- ageing time curve,
(b) Elastic modulus-ageing time curve

were very fine. However, the precipitate did not uniformly distribute in the micro-scale level. There existed precipitation clusters and precipitation-poor zones. In addition, most SiCp were surrounded by the fine precipitation. This may be the reason for the increase of elastic modulus after ageing. The precipitation may modify the interface between Mg matrix and SiCp through precipitating at the interface. This may improve the load transfer effect of SiCp, which can also improve the elastic modulus of the composites. This needs further TEM investigation and mechanical tests.

Fig. 10 Ageing behavior of as-extruded composite
 (a) UTS- ageing time curve,
 (b) Elastic modulus-ageing time curve

3.3 Mechanical properties of the composites

The mechanical properties of the composites are shown in Table.2. Compared with AZ91D alloy, the YS, UTS and elastic modulus of as-cast composite were evidently improved. Hot extrusion significantly improved the mechanical properties of the composite. Hot extrusion can improve the particle distribution and refine the grain of matrix, which can improve the mechanical properties of the composite.

Fig. 11 Fractographs for the as-extruded composite

However, particle cracking induced by extrusion can reduce the mechanical properties of the composite. Fig.11 shows the fractographs for the as-extruded composite. It can be found that there were matrix crumbs at the surfaces of most SiCp in the fractograph, so the fracture is mainly due to decohesion of the interface. Thus, particle cracking induced by extrusion did not evidently influence the mechanical properties.

In addition, T6 treatment can significantly improve the YS, UTS and elastic modulus of both as-cast and as-extruded composites. This is

Table.2 Mechanical properties of alloy and composites

Materials	YS/MPa	UTS/MPa	E/GPa	δ /%
As-cast AZ91 alloy	72	146	43	2.2
As-cast composite	176	204	68	0.6
As-cast composite (T6)	250	293	78	0.7
As-extruded composite	345	359	71	0.7
As-extruded composite (T4)	337	361	70	0.9
As-extruded composite (T6)	381	396	82	1.4

mainly due to the large number of fine and lamellate precipitations.

4 Conclusions

- (1) The mechanical stir assisted by ultrasonic method can be used to fabricate bulk 20% SiCp/AZ91 composites. The mechanical properties of composite were evidently improved.
- (2) The particle content and particle distribution was similar in different positions of bulk composite ingot. Thus, the particle distribution was uniform in general. However, particles were segregated along grain boundaries in the micro-scale level, forming necklace-type distribution.
- (3) Hot extrusion significantly improved the particle distribution of the composite, although many particles were cracked during hot extrusion. Thus, extrusion effectively improved the mechanical properties of the composite.
- (4) T6 treatment evidently improved the YS, UTS and elastic modulus of both as-cast and as-extruded composites due to the large number of fine and lamellate precipitations.

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